

Patents for Science - Chances and Challenges (Preprint)

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Abstract

Even though the informational value of patents is widely acknowledged, the actual use of patent information in a non-industry settings among scientists is low. This leads to the formation of systematic blind spots within research communities with numerous undesirable effects. While some evidence-based grasp on this situation exists, our understanding, in particular regarding possible improvement paths, remains inadequate. In an effort to shed further light on the situation, we conducted a survey among 193 participants from six German research institutes on the current use and potential of patents in science. Our main findings include that the complexity of the information space as well as efficiency constraints are the strongest factors in the inhibition of use. A better integration of relevant sources, interlinking among objects of interest, and targeted extraction of relevant sections from patent documents all can serve to help scientists access and exploit crucial information.

Keywords: Patents, User Survey, Scientific Use

1. Introduction

According to estimates, more than 70% of the total technical knowledge of humankind is described in patents [1]. And without a doubt, the information contained therein has a high value for solving important technological and scientific questions, such as the identification of existing solutions for faced problems [2, 3]. Numerous study findings support that knowledge derived from patents is of great importance, especially for technology-oriented re-

search areas and applied sciences [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]. Yet, this potential remains underused in the scientific context [10, 11].

It is widely believed that the reasons are, on the one hand, the lack of expertise of researchers in using existing tools, and, on the other hand, the complexity and specialization of patent information (PI). The situation has been exacerbated by the fact that the evolution of such existing tools has often catered to the needs of patent experts, leaving the majority of the scientific community to fend for themselves. Crucially, we note that the systematic examination of these hypotheses is lacking. Indeed, as has been observed previously, “[t]here is relatively little evidence, however, about whether researchers actually read patents. Previously published surveys pre-date the ready availability of patents online and have generally been focused on managers or lawyers rather than researchers, leaving many open questions about whether patent disclosures in fact provide a benefit worth closer scrutiny [. . .]” [10, p. 421].

In order to determine the extent to which patents have been used in the scientific context to date, to record the need for scientifically relevant information in patent data, and to establish a better understanding of researchers’ motivations as well as information needs, FIZ Karlsruhe conducted a survey among scientists at six research institutes of the Leibniz Association (cf. section 4).

The survey was set up online with a mix of single, multiple choice and free text questions for a total of 27 questions, taking into account the findings of said previous studies [10, 11, 1]. A major purpose of the study was to investigate the value of patents as an important source of information for the increasingly interdisciplinary sciences, e.g. for technology and innovation analysis, for determining the state of the art, for learning from existing solutions, and for the prevention of unintentional duplication of research.

From that vantage, it is apparent that it is crucial for researchers to know the patent situation for their own field as well as in other relevant fields, in addition to the current scientific literature (SL). Particularly as the path over patents can lead to new insights from linked (cited) prior art found in non-patent literature.

We therefore set out to understand the requirements of the target groups under consideration in the context of their own research. One of our main goals was to derive insights which would assist in the conceptualization and subsequent realization of an adequate, innovative information infrastructure for the in-depth use of patent information for scientists.

2. Results

The survey can be roughly divided into four parts. In the first part, we asked respondents some general information questions regarding their positions, ages, and areas of expertise. In the second part, we asked about foraging behavior with respect to scientific information needs. The third part went on to gather information regarding patent information use. And finally, a few questions were concerned with legal aspects.

2.1. General Survey Population

Most of the respondents were scientists (58%), with (Junior) Group Leaders in second place (21.2%). There were eight PhD candidates (4.1%) and seven respondents worked in the capacity of patent manager or information professional (3.6%) We captured the age distribution in three buckets: less than 35 years old (39.4%), 35 to 50 years old (39.9%), and above 50 years of age (20.7%). Information regarding areas of expertise were captured in a fairly fine-grained manner, generally the backgrounds were from physics, chemistry, engineering, and material sciences.

2.2. Scientific Information Use

In order to be able to contrast findings, we did not only ask for PI use behavior, but also for typical scientific information use patterns. The top three platforms for searching for SL turned out to be Google Scholar, ResearchGate, and Web of Science (cf. Fig. 1). After that, widespread use drops off quickly.

The top two goals for SL searches included exploring the state of the art (89.6%) and finding details of descriptions on scientific methods and approaches (78.8%). After that, specific details (60.6%), experiments (49.2%), and research trends (47.7%) were next, followed by a large gap to simulation and modeling (7.3%), and, in last place, the “other” category with only 3%, indicating that the choices we provided did indeed cover the most important aspects.

2.3. Legal Perspective

Beyond scientific interests, patent readers’ two main reasons for interest in legal aspects are to determine if their research may be patentable (56%) or to find out if they may be infringing existing patents (42%).

Figure 1: Use of scientific information platforms

Interestingly, while in [10] it was found that “[l]egal scholars have stated that willful infringement rules prevent researchers from reading patents”, none of the respondents in our survey gave indication that this is a concern for non-for-profit research institutes in Germany. We are, however, aware of such concerns in industry settings.

Asked if they thought that other researchers’ patents hindered their own research, only 10.6% answered affirmative, while 47.2% were unsure, and 37.3% were sure that this was not the case.

Legal events pertaining to patent data are less well known with 11%, if patent professionals are not counted even less with 7%. Regarding the legal status of patents it would be helpful to know that not all once granted patents are still alive, and that not all patents that show up as expired or lapsed are truly out of the game. Thus, while in many applications such legal considerations are ranging from paramount to nice to consider, e.g. to improve the data basis for a large scale analytical survey, for researchers, their main interests could often be satisfied without regard to this complex set of issues (cf. section 2.4.2).

2.4. Patent Information Use

Out of the 193 respondents, 142 claimed some familiarity with patent information while 51 professed to not know about PI at all. This ratio (74% to 26%) is similar to the one observed in [10], with 78% to 22% among the non-industry cohort. Interestingly, in our survey the age distribution among those unfamiliar with PI revealed 27 (52%) to be under 35, while in the general cohort the under 35-year-olds are 39%. This suggests that younger scientists may be at a particular disadvantage when it comes to PI.

Those that do know about patents peruse the information with highly reduced frequency in comparison to scientific literature. While 76% of respondents search daily or at least weekly for SL, not a single respondent searches daily for patents and only 7% weekly (cf. Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Frequencies of searching in patents or scientific literature in percent

There are multiple reasons for this. Notably, entry and access barriers play an important role. Among those that do not read patents at all, the most frequent argument was “Hard to understand jargon” (43.1%), followed by “Don’t know how to find relevant patents” (35.3%), “Patents do not contain useful information” (35.3%), and “Finding relevant patents is too time-consuming” (23.5%).

Also, readers of patents will know that there is a large difference between texts and headings in patent full texts and in scholarly papers. Whereas scholarly papers are, by and large, concise and well-readable, with a familiar and coherent structure, patents come with more obstacles. To begin with,

the claims section is not relevant to many scientific information needs and may act as a distractor. The abstracts may also not be particularly helpful. At least in professional patent search communities, it is well established that inventor/assignee abstracts are often not helpful in determining relevancy regarding specific information requests.

This leaves the areas of description and images. Images can indeed be very useful, but they require a multimodal representation and therefore pose other challenges.

2.4.1. Patent Document Structure

The overall familiarity with structure and peculiarities of patents appears fairly good as far as the bibliography and fulltext sections are concerned (59.9% and 53.5%). However, even among people familiar with PI in general, classifications appear to be not well known. 43.7% answered they knew none of the schemes, whereas 41.5% knew the IPC¹ scheme. Astonishingly, even though in force since 2013 and designed to be the successor of the IPC, the CPC² scheme is still widely unknown (7.7%). In the under-35 age range just one person knew about the CPC, whereas 17 persons knew about the IPC (22.4%). Given that the classifications can offer considerable help for search and analysis, this is a clear area for either education or for tools to better implicitly or explicitly leverage that information for users.

Patent families are fairly little known (27%). Those are collections of patents that cover the same invention. E.g. in a simple case, an invention is granted a patent in the US and is granted a patent in Japan. Those two patents form a family. The investigation of family relations can serve many purposes, for a scientific information searcher, a prime use could be to use them to shrink the size of data one has to consider on a per-document basis. This is something where the onus should not fall on the user but on the tool.

2.4.2. Information Need of Scientists

The main objectives for scientists using PI lie in trying to find information regarding methods and processes (71.8%) and technical specifications (60.6%). This is broadly comparable to the goals in literature search (cf. section 2.2).

¹International Patent Classification

²Cooperative Patent Classification

Figure 3: Assessment of methods regarding their helpfulness.

While some motivation exists to search patents for prior art, the interest to cite a patent just like a scientific reference is comparably low (27%). Competitor observation ranks higher (38.7%), but search for partners, either for projects (9.2%) or for the commercial exploitation of own research (7.0%), is low. Mostly, patents are read to observe current developments (54.9%), which is remarkable, given the 18 month delay between application and the publication of the application. The two most sought-after methods were automated analysis of datasets and automated knowledge discovery in these datasets. Here, 54.2% stated (automated) technology analysis of SL and PI would help, while 46.5% consider (automated) knowledge discovery (cf. Fig. 3) would be a plus.

Thus, it seems researchers are to some extent aware, that a full picture of current developments cannot be gathered from SL alone. Only 5.6% indicated that they had no idea if any useful knowledge would be hidden in patents.

Integrate Patents with Scientific Literature?

Figure 4: Linking patents and scientific literature.

80% of respondents believe that integrating patent search and scientific literature search (Fig. 4) would or may help with their information foraging.

2.4.3. Qualitative Feedback

The survey offered opportunities to provide free text feedback. In such comments, a recurrent theme is the difficulty of identifying the valuable information in patents. Often, commentators observed that patents seemed to be written in a way to conceal the topic matter and precise functioning. As one person put it: “Most patents state that something works, but not why it works. Integrating scientific literature and patent information could solve this problem.”

Other people are concerned about quality aspects regarding all information sources: “I don’t think that integrating scientific literature and patent information would help because both fields are flooded with useful and less useful information.”

And thirdly, there is the observation that patents offer unique insights: “Some organisations, especially industry, are often not interested in writing scientific papers. In these cases patents are the only source of information for the public.”

Taken together with the quantitative data before, this qualitative feedback helps establish a comprehensive picture, which shall be discussed in the following section.

3. Discussion

Patent information is underused in scientific contexts. We gathered information through surveys to support this general observation with hard data. It became apparent that scientists are strongly interested in the use of relevant patent information beyond the typical use cases of the IP business (Prior Art, Freedom to Operate, Infringement, etc.). In addition to researching the state of the art and learning from existing solutions, scientists would also like to observe competitors and gain insights into current developments and trends.

However, patent search is an activity that runs in a separate, much less frequently employed process than scientific literature search. The reasons for this range from time-constraints over accessibility concerns to the complexities of identifying the sought-after information in patents. The impact of patent information shows up when used and taken into account within the scientific value creation process of researchers, where knowledge, e.g., the description of technical procedures, chemical substances, methods and

processes, is of great importance for research on technological and scientific questions.

For example, by reviewing patents in their own field, researchers can identify potential improvements to existing technologies and develop new, innovative solutions for existing problems. Furthermore, researchers can avoid inadvertently infringing on existing patents and avoid costly legal disputes when directly incorporating patents into their research. However, available infrastructures are inadequate to realize an integrated and supportive information access to patent information, as also shown by the results of the survey and the concluded fact that patent knowledge is not easily accessible to researchers. Therefore, linking patents to scientific literature and domain-specific information will allow for a more easy access to relevant patents, hence, help to better discover essential knowledge in patent text. From the technological point of view, patents have to be enriched and linked with relevant scientific information sources adding more contextual information for understanding the underlying research context of the regarded invention and its embodiment.

It is apparent that adopting the FAIR and Linked Open Data (LOD) principles [12] for patent data holds immense potential in this regard. An infrastructure making patent knowledge findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable can empower next generation services for search & analytics for researchers, giving them easier access to relevant patent information and a better understanding of the technological and theoretical background of inventions. Moreover, this allows to directly integrate patent information with related scientific literature and research data—and vice versa.

Depending on the domain and the research question, further (subject-specific) knowledge is required to achieve this.

4. Methods

The presented results rely on the aggregated data from surveys among six German research institutes. All institutes involved in the survey belong to the Leibniz Association and are not-for-profit research institutes outside of the university system. The underlying English-language questionnaire was adapted to the circumstances of the respective institute (e.g. adaptation of the research topics) and all individual surveys were conducted online using

SurveyMonkey³.

Primarily, the study was focused on questions about innovative uses of patent information and the identification of concrete needs but also possible barriers among participants. Therefore, in addition to scientists, research-related individuals such as technical staff, managers, etc. from various disciplines and fields were selected as the target group.

To gain better insight into the respondent population, the collected data not only encompassed the professional position, but also the age group and the research focus.

We provided our contacts at the respective institutes with information regarding the background and the scope of the survey and asked them to disseminate it as they saw fit. The surveys usually ran for two weeks and were extended for another seven days, if necessary, depending on the response rate. The overall timeframe was April 2020 to May 2021. We received 193 responses in total.

5. Competing Interests

The authors declare no competing financial or non-financial interests.

6. Data Availability

6.1. *Supplementary information*

Merged survey responses from the 193 participants are publicly available for download at: <https://zenodo.org/record/8085719>

6.2. *Acknowledgments*

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³<https://www.surveymonkey.com/>

6.3. Author Contributions

H.A.: Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims; Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyse or synthesize study data; Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre- or post-publication stages.

M.M.B.: Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre- or post-publication stages.

R.H.-S.: Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyse or synthesize study data; Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft.

7. Code Availability

For data aggregation and postprocessing we used KNIME⁴, version 4.5.1.

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